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RESEARCH ARTICLE

CURRICULAR IMPLICATIONS OF KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT FOR LIBRARY AND INFORMATION SCIENCE EDUCATION IN NIGERIA

Tunde Toyese Oyedokun^a, Medinat Dolapo Laaro^b, Zainab Olanihun Ambali^c, Saidat Ranmilowo Komolafe^d^aUniversity of Ilorin Faculty of Communication and Information Sciences, Ilorin, Kwara State Nigeria^bMaster of Library and Information Science, Kwara State College of Arabic and Islamic Legal Studies, Ilorin, Nigeria. ^cMaster of Library and Information Science, University Library, University of Ilorin, Ilorin, Nigeria^dMaster of Library and Information Science, Osun State University Library, Osogbo, Osun State, Nigeria*Corresponding Author e-mail: toyex4eternity@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

The introduction of knowledge management into the library and information science curriculum comes with some implications that bordered on how knowledge management is being taught and represented in the curriculum design for LIS education. The investigation was carried out from the viewpoint of LIS community in Nigeria using a web-based survey questionnaire and interview. Certified librarians in Nigeria constitute the unit of analysis; their population stood at 6,504, and only 369 participants completed the survey, followed by interviews with five professors from library schools in Nigeria. The result from findings indicated that from the six variables raised on the implications of knowledge management on library and information science education, only two variables score above the Mean Variable Score ($X=3.98$) benchmark, the need for KM competencies to be fully integrated into the LIS curriculum score the highest mean score ($X=4.46$), followed by the need for the LIS curriculum to keep changing to accommodate new development in KM. It also manifested in the study that the current curriculum did not adequately equip LIS professionals for knowledge management practice. More so, knowledge management can be treated as a separate course on its own and as well be integrated into the existing library and information science courses. From the seven knowledge management concepts and themes raised, only four variables score above the Mean Variable Score ($X=4.32$) benchmark, interpersonal relationship leads the pact with a mean score ($X=4.39$), followed by research and evaluation with a mean score ($X=4.38$), knowledge management tools, technics and technologies with a mean score ($X=4.36$) and lastly leadership and managerial role with a mean score ($X=4.35$). Also from the four variables raised on responsibilities of LIS schools, two of the variables score above the Mean Variable Score ($X=4.4$) benchmark, need for LIS schools to train and retrain LIS educators score the highest mean score ($X=4.45$) followed by the need for LIS schools to collaborate with other allied disciplines in the design and training of LIS professionals for KM with a mean score ($X=4.4$). This implies that effective training and education for KM calls for cooperation and collaboration among different academic units.

KEYWORDS

Knowledge Management, Librarianship, Library School, Curriculum, Library and Information Science Education, Certified Librarian of Nigeria.

1. INTRODUCTION

Knowledge is the most vital resource in today's knowledge-driven society, such that the success of any organization largely depends on effective management of vital information resources and that of the un-captured expertise knowledge of its workforce. In the wake of this, knowledge management practice becomes an essential instrument through which an organization could gain a competitive advantage over its competitors. Most essentially, knowledge management is the systematic and strategic management of both tacit and explicit knowledge in the pursuance of organizational objectives. It a process that revolves around the extraction of knowledge (wherever they reside or deposited) from an organization's intellectual capital and as such builds on intelligence to improve organizational performance. The whole functionalities of knowledge management could be encapsulated into processes that involve sharing of

information, idea, perspective and experience that help to align knowledge discovery with innovation in an organization.

Knowledge management integrates people, processes, technology, organizational structure and most importantly harnesses the organization's intellectual capital for easy adaptation in the face of change in the environment where an organization operates. The relationship between organizational structure and knowledge management is interdependence such that, while organization structure reflects a hierarchical line of authority, communication, and chain of command, knowledge management on the other hand provides the basis for redirecting the organization structure to enhance performance (Wahba, 2015). Organizational structure influences the effective implementation of knowledge management, most especially when the characteristics of such organizational structure are less centralized, formalized and more

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integrated. The organizational structure most suitable for effective knowledge management initiative is that that is flexible, easily adaptable to change as well as one that encourages a free flow of information and communication.

Knowledge management is a multi-disciplinary domain that encompasses many fields of study. This accounted for why there is hardly any universally accepted definition of knowledge management, as there are various dimensions to its interpretation and definition. Its multiplicity nature is reflected in how it is being contextualized and conceptualized among various scholars and researchers from a different educational background. For example, interpret knowledge management from the library and information science background by associating it with a concept that control knowledge needs as an important resource in the provision of quality and dynamic library and information services (Balague et al., 2015). Also, the International Federation of Library Association (IFLA) gave knowledge management definition that includes concepts and skills required for library work and professional development outside traditional library services such as processes that involve creating, storing, sharing, applying and reusing of organizational knowledge to attain organizational goals and objectives (IFLA, 2015).

Librarianship like knowledge management is an interdisciplinary field of study, which integrates the practices, perspectives, and tools of information technology, management science, education and other allied fields of studies. Today digital age has transformed the process of information access and information retrieval, so library and information science schools are now on the journey of passing through a complex and dynamic educational restructuring. In reflection to this, opined that library and information science schools should commensurate library and information science professionals' competencies with today's information needs of users since educational programs are always open to change (Thanuskodi, 2012). Therefore, the curriculum for LIS education must keep changing in line with the dictate of new development in the society.

Traditional library and information management skills form an integer part of knowledge management formation, processes and spectrum. This is to say that information tools, techniques and technology exerted in information management is practically applicable to a great extent also to knowledge management practice. Besides, additional competencies in areas such as leadership skills, communication and interpersonal relationship skills, change management skills, cognitive management skills, advanced information technology skills as well as broader skills for management of individual's working experience that also involves the management of collective organizational intellectual capital is required. Knowledge management was substantiated to be a fusion of activities that are closely related and even connected with the library's information management functionalities. In congruence to forgoing, postulated that many knowledge management activities are interwoven and overlapped with most library and information management functions, that the philosophical assumptions underlying library practice is synonymous with that of knowledge management since the fundamental roles of library and information science professionals were to select, acquire, organize, store, disseminate and preserve knowledge for posterity (Oyedokun et al., 2018). Sequel to the need to train new era library and information science professionals for knowledge management competencies, constitute the hallmark that necessitates the need for the introduction of knowledge management into the curriculum for library and information science education (Oyedokun et al., 2018; Harinee et al., 2015; National Universities Commission, 2014). Also advocating for this annexation was who asserted that knowledge management is an important subject that needed to be integrated into the curriculum of library and information science to equip library and information science professionals for wider job opportunities (Alegbeleye, 2010). As stated in apposition, knowledge management enriches the curriculum of library and information science education, for the profession to be more lucrative for librarians in training and more attractive to aspiring students. It also proffers an avenue and training ground for LIS professionals to expand their roles and duties beyond the four walls of the library.

Be that as it may, library and information science education include training and practice of knowledge management, and they were being offered at the various higher institution of learning in Nigeria which includes; colleges, polytechnics and universities. These institutions awarded certificates ranging from diploma, bachelor's degree, master's degree as well as doctorate with varying contents, nomenclatures and grading system subject to the discretion of the awarding institution (Diso and Njoku, 2007). Certifications awarded in the universities are those recognized by law (Act No. 2 of June 15, 1995) of Librarians' Registration Council of Nigeria (LRCN) as a prerequisite to practice as a professional

librarian, Bachelor of library and information science is the minimum requirement while certifications from other institutions such as polytechnics and colleges are for the training of para-professionals or library assistances. Library and information science professionals recognized by law in Nigeria are those trained in LRCN and National Universities Commission's (NUC) accredited library schools (Abubakar and Farouk, 2016).

Section 10 (1) of the Education Act (National Minimum Standards and Establishment of Institutions) Cap E3, Laws of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 2004 bestowed upon the National Universities Commission of Nigeria (NUC) the power and jurisdiction to accredit and as well determine the Minimum Academic Standard (MAS) for all programs taught in all Nigeria universities (NUC, 2014; Amaechi et al., 2018). The commission in 2001 subject the instrument for accreditation, Minimum Academic Standard (MAS) to review because of the increase in the frontier of knowledge, advancement in information and communication technology (ICT) as well as impact of globalization on all disciplines of study. In the cause of ensuring that universities in Nigeria trained students with appropriate skills, competencies and disposition to make them globally competitive, the commission, therefore, comes up with a revised document titled: Benchmark Minimum Academic Standards (BMAS) for accreditation of courses in Nigeria universities (NUC, 2014). Library and information science as a field of study in some universities in Nigeria was not immune from the bane of review the instrument of accreditation was subjected to, as more courses most especially in the area of ICT competencies are introduced into the curriculum and another noticeable inclusion was knowledge management.

Inclusion of knowledge management in the curriculum of library and information science education into the Benchmark Minimum Academic Standards (BMAS) for accreditation of LIS courses in Nigeria was a result of clamoring from LIS professionals in Nigeria, and a prominent figure among them is who posited that NUC curriculum benchmark of 2007 did not make provision for courses such as entrepreneurship and knowledge management but barely make provisions for Library Automation only with a course, that seems not adequate to capture all the ICT competencies require of today new era librarians (Aina, 2014). The International Federation of Library Association (IFLA) also reflected on the relevance of knowledge management to librarianship. The association in 2003 developed a program of activities that support LIS professionals in the implementation of a knowledge management program in their various organizations. This has given rise to a discussion of issues among scholars and researchers as to how knowledge management is related to librarianship. The progression and prospect of knowledge management elicit dominant challenges to the existing LIS education structure, in particular on how it is being taught and represented in the curriculum for LIS education (Zhou et al., 2018).

The introduction of knowledge management into the curriculum of library and information science comes with some implications that bordered on how knowledge management is being taught and represented in the curriculum design for library and information science education, core concepts and themes of knowledge management worthy of inclusion in LIS curriculum as well as responsibilities of library schools in ensuring knowledge management competencies of new era library and information science professionals. However, the best way to integrate knowledge management into LIS education is still a subject of debate among library and information science educators and researchers. Some researchers advocated for integration with already existing courses such as library management and information management while others go for a separate course of its own, indifferent among them is who advocated for both expansions of the content of already existing courses to accommodate themes and concepts of knowledge management and also as a separate course of its own (Nwosu, 2016). Despite the deepness and richness of literature on the relationship between librarianship and knowledge management, yet a scanty of publications on curricular implications of knowledge management for LIS education most especially in Nigeria where the current study was conducted. Bridging this empirical gap was this study was geared towards achieving.

1.1 Statement of the Research Problem

Knowledge management goes beyond traditional library practice, where the emphasis is mainly on recorded knowledge. For instance, skills like business intelligence, managerial skills and advance IT competencies required for effective knowledge management practice have not been adequately catered for in the LIS curriculum. Knowledge management is encyclopedic, and as such transcends many disciplines such as business administration, library and information science, artificial intelligence,

organizational science, computer science and many more. The multidisciplinary nature of knowledge management accounted for its program and training found scattered around various field of studies with each affiliated discipline placing focus in areas of knowledge management that emphasize key aspect of their disciplines. This is what is responsible for the many approaches to its teaching, training and curriculum development (Harper, 2013). For instance, knowledge management in the business world emphasizes leadership strategy, business intelligence, organizational culture, collaboration and knowledge economy system. Computer science emphasizes on technology and information architectural aspect of knowledge management, while the focus of library and information science is on knowledge organization, preservation and dissemination (Dalkir et al., 2016).

However, the multidimensional nature of knowledge management posed the challenge of finding a common ground or broad consensus on what course content of knowledge management is suitable for LIS education. Aside that, it is also difficult to determine the intellectual territory to be covered because knowledge management did not easily fit-in into a singular academic discipline; hardly is an ideal academic place or unit for knowledge management, hence, designing an educational program for a complex multidisciplinary subject like knowledge management seems very daunting for library schools most especially those in Nigeria.

1.2 Research Questions

The following are research questions answered by the study:

1. What curricular implications does knowledge management have on library and information science education in Nigeria?
2. What themes and concepts of knowledge management are worthy of inclusion in the curriculum design of the library and information science?
3. What are the responsibilities of library and information schools in ensuring adequate knowledge management competencies of library and information science professionals?

2. RELATED LITERATURE

Libraries are knowledge storehouses and intellectual hubs whilst knowledge management is an essential building block for the provision of quality and dynamic information services. Because of this, LIS professionals are duty-bound to be conversant with how organizational knowledge could be managed and applied to render services that offer users maximum satisfaction. Knowledge management proffers LIS professionals the opportunity to expand their boundaries into wider job possibilities. With higher competencies in knowledge management, LIS professionals can undertake roles in any organization and their job portfolio might be outside librarianship but with job titles such as knowledge officer/manager, knowledge management specialist, knowledge management analyst, knowledge management consultant, content manager and many more. It is an indisputable fact that the introduction of knowledge management into LIS education enhances LIS professionals' career development (Oyedokun et al., 2018; Harineeswaran et al., 2015).

Librarianship and knowledge management are affiliated, such that library functionalities manifested either explicitly or quietly in almost all knowledge management processes. And over the years, most LIS schools have realized the importance of incorporating knowledge management programs into their curriculum, but they are still in vogue on whether to integrate the program into the existing course(s) or as a separate course on its own. A group researcher emphasized that library and information science professionals already possessed some competencies that are very relevant for knowledge management, that knowledge management should only be integrated into the curriculum of library and information science rather than being studying as a separate course (Zhou et al., 2018). This assertion was in advocacy with expression, who stated that pursuing a higher degree in knowledge management is more or less vying for the position of vice-president (Sinotte, 2004). This is to say that whatsoever skills or competencies that could be required for knowledge management, library and information science professionals already possessed the basic skills. Similarly, also posited that knowledge management is a special management subject that needed to be integrated with library management along with other management and business topics such as quality management, project management, human resource management, marketing and public relation (Georgy et al., 2005). Also advocating for the inclusion of KM into LIS curriculum was who stressed that the inclusion of knowledge management into the library and information science curriculum will make library and information science education more

appealing to potential aspirants (Logan and Hsieh-Yee, 2001).

Library schools are perceived to be more active in the teaching of knowledge management more than business and management schools do. This was because LIS professionals see knowledge management as an extension of information management and traditional library services. In the case of China, for instance, knowledge management gains prominent among Chinese educators and researchers in the early years of the 2000s as a new ground for management research that is capable of promoting organization efficiency. By 2005 educational framework for knowledge management education has already been proposed as a benchmark for universities in China. Despite the early dominance of knowledge management in the business world, notwithstanding, knowledge management was more valued in library schools when interest and responses from business and management schools are compared. The School of Information Management, Wuhan University offered the first broad in content knowledge management module both in its undergraduate and postgraduate library and information science program. The knowledge management module in Wuhan library school covers only the basics, which could be considered obsolete as more and more knowledge management tools, technics and technology keep emerging almost every day. In the wake of this, knowledge management education schemes need to be developed through the collaborative efforts of LIS and other KM educators and researchers (Zhou et al., 2018; Zhou et al., 2017).

2.1 Evolution of Library and Information Science Education in Nigeria

Library and information science education in Nigeria have come a long way since the establishment of the first library school at University College, Ibadan on the recommendation of the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) Seminar of 1953 (Edegbo, 2011). Elaborating on the account of events that took place after, was who specifically stated that library school started as an institute of librarianship (now the department of the library, archive and information studies) in 1959, and six (6) students were enrolled for the postgraduate diploma in librarianship in 1960 (Abioye, 2013). Before independence, during the colonial era when there were no library schools in Nigeria, librarianship was a non-graduate profession because there were relatively few graduates in the country (Aguolu and Aguolu, 2002). Libraries in the country were being manned by expatriates while indigenes that were aspiring to become a librarian went to Britain to qualify for the certification of British Library Association with preparation training given to them by practicing librarians through short courses. Another notable program for the training of librarians was the one organized by Achimota library school in Gold Coast (now Ghana) in 1944, jointly financed by Carnegie Corporation, British Council and governments of the three (3) participating countries (Nigeria, Ghana and Sierra Leone) which was slated to last for experimental period of three (3) years. The library school admitted fourteen (14) candidates of which six (6) are Nigerian. Another initiative was a combined effort of the library staff of University College, Ibadan and British Council libraries that were organizing training for various categories of library staff from other parts of the country (Aguolu and Aguolu, 2002; Okiy, 2014).

Today, the historical evolution of library and information science education in Nigeria demonstrated a continual empirical search for relevance and appropriateness of skills and training for new era librarians. The library and information science profession had metamorphosed from apprenticeship method of education to certification from the British Library Association (before independent) now to a standardized formal education with geographical relevance that provides two avenues for professionalism, one at the undergraduate level and the other at postgraduate level (Aguolu and Aguolu, 2002). Also worthy of note in the evolutionary development of library and information science education in Nigeria was the promulgation of Decree (now Act) No 2 of June 15, 1995, that foresees the establishment of the Librarians' Registration Council of Nigeria (LRCN) who was saddled with the responsibility of determining who is a professional librarian, setting the standard of knowledge for skills acquisition and accreditation of courses for library and information science education as well as coordination of seminars, conferences and workshops for librarians' capacity building in Nigeria (LRCN, 2018). Advancement in information and communication technology (ICT), globalization as well as a change in users' preference for web-based information services necessitates the need for periodic review and revamping of library and information science curricula.

2.2 Knowledge Management Processes

Knowledge management is all about building organizational intelligence

to improve performance. It provides an organization with tools to improve on ways to capture, share and use knowledge, that helps in building the experience of an organizational workforce and to ensure better practices, strategies and policies in an organization. The knowledge management process, on the other hand, is a step-by-step approach or stages or even continuum through which the intellectual capital of an organization was developed. Scholars and researchers suggested several processes, but the one that the researchers found suitable for this current study was that of Nigeria Governors' Forum (Tasmin et al., 2012; Seleim and Khalid, 2011; Martins et al., 2001; Wiig, 1990; Gartner group, 1998).

The Nigeria Governors' Forum (NGF) embarked on knowledge management initiatives because of the notion that knowledge is one of the key measures of excellent performance. The knowledge management initiative at the Nigeria Governors' Forum was set out to support easy access to information for efficient internal management; to oversee and maintain the NGF content on the intranet and website by liaison with the publication press unit of the NGF and to ensure that all events and contacts are uploaded promptly; to ensure an effective process of extracting, analyzing, and disseminating lessons learned from NGF activities; to ensure regular and relevant information is shared among all staff to improve the learning process across project stakeholders. The Nigeria Governors' Forum's knowledge management process is in a continuum that revolved around knowledge auditing, knowledge creation, knowledge capturing, knowledge storage, knowledge sharing and knowledge application. The figure below illustrated the continuum.

Figure 1: Nigeria Governors' Forum's Knowledge Management Cycle.
(Source: NGF, 2012).

The six (6) processes involved in knowledge management as identified by NGF (2012) are explained below:

Knowledge Auditing: knowledge auditing is an essential assessment of knowledge needs and knowledge sources within an organization that takes into account tacit and explicit knowledge (Skyrme, 2013). Knowledge auditing is a systematic and independent inspection of where a particular organization stands in terms of its knowledge capacity. Essentially, it is an investigation into the knowledge health of the organization. It presents a comprehensive picture of the strengths and weaknesses of an organization's knowledge capacity.

Knowledge Creation: Knowledge creation is the ability of an individual or organization to create new knowledge through a continuous transfer, combination and conversion of both tacit and explicit knowledge. A group researcher thought that sharing of experience is an important element of the knowledge creation process, most especially when dealing with tacit knowledge (Botha et al., 2008). Establishing an enabling environment that encourages brainstorming, trial and error, informal interaction and intuition will boost the knowledge creation process in an organization. Some researchers identified four (4) types of knowledge creation processes, namely: Socialization, Externalization, Combination and Internalization (Nonaka and Takeuchi, 2004).

Knowledge Capturing: other researchers defined knowledge capturing as a process through which knowledge is being converted from tacit to explicit and vice versa through externalization and internalization of tacit or explicit knowledge (Becerra-Fernandez and Sabherwal, 2010). Externalization takes place when an organization captures the tacit knowledge of its staff for documentation and verbalization. Internalization, on the other hand, is the process through which workers acquire tacit knowledge. Capturing knowledge also includes collecting relevant documents and organizing them for easy retrieval. Capturing knowledge may also require interviewing with knowledge workers.

Knowledge Storage: Knowledge that is considered a vital resource that enhances individual and organization performance is worthy of

consideration of effort for documentation, storage and preservation. This knowledge can be stored in an organization's repository where it can be accessed (Koech et al., 2013).

Knowledge Sharing: Knowledge sharing is the process of transferring or disseminating knowledge from an individual or group to another in an organization. Knowledge sharing could also be seen as intentional sharing of awareness and experience among learners with the aims of enriching their knowledge and as well create or maintain a repository for reusable knowledge

Knowledge Application: Applying knowledge involves putting to use the available knowledge to make the right decision and perform a task by following a direction and performing some routines. By direction we mean the process through which individuals that possessed the knowledge direct the action of another without transferring the actual knowledge, performance, on the other hand, involves using knowledge embedded in the process, procedure and rule to guide future behavior (Becerra-Fernandez and Sabherwal, 2010). The whole process involved in knowledge management proves to be a futile endeavor if the knowledge is not consistently used and apply.

2.3 Relationship between Knowledge Management and Library Practice

Knowledge management and librarianship are allied discipline such that most of the tools, techniques and technologies used in knowledge management also applies to information management (Oyedokun et al., 2018; Muthu et al., 2013). The only distinguishing feature is that knowledge management is essentially a mechanism for the utilization of collective knowledge of the entire workforce to achieve organizational goals. These distinguishing features demarcate knowledge management from traditional library practice, as the emphasis of knowledge management is more on tacit knowledge while that of a library is on recorded knowledge (explicit knowledge). A good knowledge management practice is all about getting the right knowledge to the right person at the right time and at the right place, which commensurate with what new era library and information science professionals are been trained for (Harineeswaran et al., 2015; Mchombu, 2010). Nigeria Governors' Forum emphasized six (6) stages of the knowledge management process (Nigeria Governors' Forum, 2012). These include knowledge auditing, knowledge creation, knowledge capturing, knowledge storage, knowledge sharing and knowledge application. The subsequent paragraphs explain the relationship between the knowledge management process and library practice:

Knowledge auditing is a critical evaluation of organization knowledge assets that showcases an evidence-based assessment of where an organization needs to focus its knowledge management effort. It also reveals organization knowledge needs, strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats. This commensurate with what library and information science professionals do when they carried out community analysis of users and collections evaluation. By community analysis, we mean the processes involved in the collection of information about the library and its community of users, which constitute an integral part of library planning. This analysis revealed users' information needs (through analysis of their demographic profiles), factors in the environment that prevent the effective provision of dynamic information services. Collections evaluation on the other hand provides insight on the breadth and depth of library holdings, available format, use pattern, length of service as well as efficiency and effectiveness of communication and networking (Library Journal, 2020; Semertzaki, 2017). The purpose of library collection auditing or evaluation is to gain confidence that library holdings are being managed and utilized effectively.

Knowledge creation is one of the essential elements of the knowledge management process that emphasized employees' skills, expertise and experience in creating new knowledge through brainstorming sessions, scientific research as well as internalization and externalization of explicit knowledge to produce new knowledge (Zamir, 2019). Knowledge creation occurs when an individual internalizes knowledge already in existence for the creation of a new one through the process of combining ideas, expatiating on present knowledge and bring in an innovation derivative of what is already in existence. By default, library and information science professionals are responsible for the selection and acquisition of information resources while researchers rely on this information on their subject area for the creation of new knowledge and innovative ideas (Hoffman, 2016). Librarians too are not found wanting in the knowledge creation process as some of their activities such as community assessment and library collection evaluation, preparation of collection development

policy, preparation of accession register, indexing and abstraction (that produce surrogate to knowledge through summarization), Bibliometrics and citation analysis, statistic takings of library operation and research on library activities, operation, trends and innovations all constitute some form of knowledge creation (Oyedokun et al., 2018).

Knowledge capturing is concerns with converting expertise knowledge of individuals from tacit to explicit so that such knowledge would not be lost to employees' retirement, turnover, or death (Becerra-Ferdinandez and Sabherwal, 2010). Library and information science professionals involved in knowledge capturing process through content and documentation management, selection of most relevant information materials from an array of available information materials, collections building and development, keeping records of users' information needs and queries, introducing new staff to work and activities as well as interacting with knowledgeable library staff for an exchange of expertise knowledge (Chaubey, 2015).

Scholars have attributed to the fact that knowledge management is more than just information management, that information management is associated with recorded knowledge while knowledge management includes both documented and undocumented knowledge (Uzuegbu and Arua, 2015). Nevertheless, knowledge organization (KO), an attribute of knowledge management is the same as librarians' work of organizing information resources in the library (Lai and Taylor, 2011). Without contradiction, knowledge organization remains the domain of library and information science professionals, which is concerned with knowledge description (metadata), indexing and categorization/classification of knowledge. This constitutes the bulk of activities that were carried out in the technical section of the library and other information providing institutions. Knowledge processing or organization is not complete without such knowledge been stored in a repository for future accessibility.

Knowledge sharing is an intentional transfer of awareness, experience and expertise among learners. Knowledge sharing is one of the core activities of knowledge management because the knowledge that was not shared is considered useless as it is not readily available for use and such knowledge is already an endangered species prone to extinction, once the original owner of the knowledge ceases to be in existence. Knowledge sharing is what library and information science professionals do in the readers' sections of the library where information materials are been circulated. This is the section of the library where knowledge materials change hands, hence knowledge is been circulated. Libraries also partake in knowledge sharing through collaboration with other information service providers in consortia and networking for resource sharing. Knowledge sharing among librarians, users and management could be initiated through the use of information technologies and applications such as Web 2.0 tools (emails, blogs, wikis, social media, etc.), workflow systems, groupware, intranet, and so on (Ugocha and Igwe, 2018).

Knowledge application is the terminal point of any knowledge management program, and it associates itself with putting knowledge to use to solve problems or to form the basis of decision making in the organization (Uzohue and Yaya, 2016). It is the sole responsibility of the management to create an enabling environment that encourages the creation, transfer and application of knowledge. It is the library management prerogative to decide whether to implement knowledge management practice in the library or not, they made the decision on which tools or techniques of knowledge management the library should adopt.

2.4 Empirical Studies

A study of curriculum enrichment for training library and information science students for entrepreneurship in the 21st Century reported curricular adjustment done at the Department of Library and Information Science, Federal Polytechnic, Unwana, Nigeria to include courses such as entrepreneurship, knowledge management, information products and services, marketing, advocacy and public relations (Igwe et al., 2016). Correspondingly, in their survey of knowledge management education provided by the member schools of the iSchools caucus around the world as well as knowledge management teaching experience in Chinese library schools (Zhou et al., 2018). From the 29 LIS schools' websites reviewed, almost all the schools had incorporated some degree of knowledge management into their curriculum either as a course module or as a unit in a related course. Knowledge management as a course is taken mostly as an elective course in most of the library schools. More so, knowledge management courses are majorly taken at the postgraduate level except in few LIS schools that offer knowledge management courses both at the undergraduate and postgraduate level.

A group researcher embarked on a study of library and information science job in Sydney Morning Herald over four weeks in each of the following year; 2004, 1994, 1984 and 1974 (Kennan et al., 2006). Their study showed that the traditional established skill of library and information science professionals in those job advertisements over the period decreased from 100% in 1974 to 44.7% in 2004. This is to say that library and information science jobs advertised in the year 1974 called for skills and competencies clearly within Library and information science domain, while job advertisement in 2004 requires competencies beyond the traditional library and information science domain. The study called upon library schools to keep developing their curriculum to one that prepares new era library and information scientists for the responsive shift in market demand and as well prepared them for jobs outside library settings.

Hazeri's study of implications of knowledge management for library and information science education observed that 62.5% of respondents agreed that knowledge management education should be a concern to library schools with a relative 21.2% not certain of the statement and 16.4% not agreeing with the assertion. Further in the study, 95.2% of the participants perceived the need to include the teaching of knowledge related competencies in the curriculum. What this study demonstrated was that knowledge management should be fully integrated into library practice, operations and curriculum for library and information science education. Similarly, a study of implications of knowledge management for library and information science profession demonstrated that 81.9% of participants agreed that education for library and information science should change to accommodate developments in knowledge management (Sarrafzadeh's, 2008).

The rationale for curriculum change was asked, respondents, 52.4% of participants (strongly agree and agree were combine) confirmed that mainstream library and information science curricula are outdated, 68.8% of participants attested to the statement that without curriculum change library and information science graduate will lose out in the labour market, 68.2% of the respondents also confirmed (strongly agree and agree were combine) that mainstream library and information science curricula did not equip library and information science professionals with adequate competencies required for knowledge management. By and large, going by the frame of literature reviewed, which indicated the involvement of LIS professionals in the core activities of knowledge management, hence, a librarian could be referred to as knowledge workers and therefore, it is high time that library schools should take a lead role in the development and training of new era library and information science professionals for knowledge management.

3. METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a survey research design since the phenomenon at hand cannot be directly observed but through the consensus of research subjects (respondents). The research strategy is inductive as it falls largely under the interpretivist paradigm of quantitative research, in that it seeks not to test variables but rather draw meaning from social context. Certified librarians in Nigeria (CLNs) constitute the unit of analysis and their population stood at 6,504 as enlisted in the Librarian's Registration Council of Nigeria's year 2020 list of certified librarians, but since total enumeration is not viable, a sample size of 3,000 certified librarians with active and functioning email were drawn using clustered random sampling technique, where 500 participants were drawn from the six (6) geopolitical zones in Nigeria (North-East, North-West, North-Central, South-West, South-East and South-South).

The instruments for data collection, questionnaire and interview guide were validated by five (5) research experts. On reliability testing of the questionnaire, the test-retest method of reliability testing was adopted where the same questionnaire was administered twice on a group of library and information science undergraduates at the University of Ilorin, Ilorin, Nigeria at an interval of two weeks. The two scores were then correlated and Cronbach alpha calculation was 0.79. The final draft of the questionnaire was administered on a web-based platform, Proprofs survey maker (<https://www.proprofs.com/survey/t/?title=knowledge-management-competency-questionnaire&token=IHRveWV4NGV0ZXJuaXR5QGdtYWlsLmNvbQ==>). The survey recorded a low response as only 369 participants completed the survey. It is this fully completed response collected from the survey that was subjected to descriptive statistical analysis. To better match findings from the surveyed LIS community, online interviews were scheduled with five professors from library schools in Nigeria on Google Form (https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSfDheAK8RyI0jQBY1mIHgHYZ5k9RnbsIF3DdjQv6YbPVYxsYQ/viewform?vc=0&c=0&w=1&usp=mail_form_link).

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF RESULT

4.1 Frequency Distribution of Sex of Pupils

Table 1: Demographic Information of the Respondents		
Demographic Information	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender: Male	221	60%
Female	148	40%
Total	369	100%
Age Bracket: Below 30	100	27%
31-40	110	29%
41-50	113	31%
51-60	40	11%
61 and above	6	2%
Total	369	100%
Geo-Political Zones : North West	77	21%
North Central	79	21%
North East	26	7%
South – South	50	14%
South East	35	9%
Total	369	100%
Highest Qualification : B.Sc/BA/BLIS	112	30%
MLS/MLIS	154	42%
PhD	96	26%
Post-PhD	7	2%
Total	369	100%
Years of Experience: 0-10	127	34%
11-20	130	35%
21-30	90	25%
31 and above	22	6%
Total	369	100%
Place of work : National Library	23	6%
Academic Library	99	27%
Public Library	36	10%
Special/Research Library	50	14%
Information Center	55	15%
Library School	67	19%
Archive/Museum	18	4%
Others	21	5%
Total	369	100%

Source: Field Survey.

Table one above presents the demographic information of the respondents (library and information science professionals in Nigeria), and it shows that 60% (221) of the respondents were males while 40% (148) were females. This implies that the survey attracted male participants than their female counterparts. Out of the 369 library and information science professionals that fully completed the survey, 31% (113) which is the highest, falls within the age bracket of 41-50 years, followed by 31-40 years that constitute 29% (110), while 27% (100), 11% (40), and 2% (6) of the participants fall between the following age range; below-30 years, 51-60 years and 61 years and above respectively.

The respondents were grouped into six (6) geopolitical zones, alongside the geographical location of their place of work or place of residence. South West zone dominates with 28% (102) participants, followed by North Central zone that has 21% (79) participants and northwest zone, having 21% (77) participants, while others like southeast zones, South-South zones and North-East zones had 14% (50), 9% (35) and 7% (26) participants respectively. The majority of the respondents are Master's holders, which constitute 42% (154) of the respondents, followed by 30% (112) who held Bachelor's degree, while 26% (96) of respondents are Ph.D. holders and 2% (7) Post-PhD holders.

Most of the respondents work in academic libraries, and they constitute 27% (99), follow by 19% (67) that lecture in library schools, and some others that work in information/documentation center which constitute 15% (55). Numbers in special/research library constitute 14% (50), that of the public library is 10% (36), those in Archival institution and museum are 4% (18), while the remaining 5% (21) works with other organizations outside those mentioned.

The table above shown the influence of knowledge management on library and information science education and it was agreed upon that library education should keep changing to accommodate new development in knowledge management, that without curriculum revamping and revising of LIS curriculum, librarians will lose out in the job market. Library schools' response to knowledge management training is inadequate and knowledge management competencies needed to be fully integrated into the curriculum. Most participants agreed that knowledge management should be treated as a separate course/subject while some favour its integration into already existing courses of library and information science. What this illustrated is that knowledge management can be treated as a course on its own and as well be integrated into the syllabus

of existing libraries and information science courses such as Collection development Management, Information management and library administration. From the six (6) variables raised on the influence of KM on LIS education, only two variables score above the Mean Variable Score (X=3.98) benchmark. The need for KM competencies to be fully integrated programs of their organization or institution.

into the LIS curriculum score the highest mean score (X=4.46), followed by the need for the LIS curriculum to keep changing to accommodate new development in KM. This implies that LIS professionals most especially those in Nigeria are ready to assume a new role and responsibility in KM

Table 2: Implications of Knowledge Management for Library and Information Science Education (N=369).

S/N	Implications of KM for LIS education	SA	A	N	D	SD	Mean	Rank	Decision
		F (%)	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)			
1	The curriculum for LIS education should change to accommodate new development in knowledge management.	159(43%)	181(49%)	12(3%)	12(3%)	5(2%)	4.29	2	Agree
2	Without curriculum change, LIS graduates will lose out on the job market.	102(28%)	175(47%)	54(15%)	27(7%)	11(3%)	3.89	3	Agree
3	The response of Library schools to knowledge management training is inadequate.	104(28%)	180(49%)	33(9%)	35(9%)	17(5%)	3.87	4	Agree
4	Knowledge management competencies needed to be integrated fully into the LIS curriculum.	192(52%) 3(1%)	164(44%)	6(2%)	4(1%)	3(1%)	4.46	1	Strongly Agree
5	Knowledge management should be treated as a separate course/subject.	125(34%)	120(33%)	45(12%)	40(11%)	39(10%)	3.68	5	Agree
6	Knowledge management should be integrated into existing courses.	104(28%)	121(33%)	86(23%)	32(9%)	26(7%)	3.66	6	Agree
Mean Variable Score									3.98

Decisions were determine using the following scoring: Strongly Agree = 4.45 to 5; Agree =3.45-4.44; Neutral =2.45-3.44; Disagree =1.45-2.44 and Strongly Disagree =1-1.44.

Source: Field Survey

Table 3: Worthiness of Inclusions of Some Knowledge Management's Themes and Concepts for the Training of Library and Information Science Professionals (N=369).

S/N	KM themes and concepts.	VH	H	M	L	VL	Mean	Rank	Decision	
		F (%)	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)				
1	The concept of Knowledge, and Knowledge management.	164(44%)	172(47%)	12(3%)	18(5%)	3(1%)	4.29	5	High	
2	Knowledge management processes.	164(44%)	167(45%)	25(7%)	3(1%)	10(3%)	4.28	6	High	
3	Knowledge management tools, techniques, and technologies.	184(50%)	149(40%)	24(6%)	9(3%)	3(1%)	4.36	3	High	
4	Interpersonal relationship: communication, teamwork, and collaboration.	185(50%)	160(43%)	11(3%)	10(3%)	3(1%)	4.39	1	High	
5	Leadership and Managerial role: human resource management.	190(51%)	141(38%)	18(5%)	17(5%)	3(1%)	4.35	4	High	
6	Research and Evaluation.	184(50%)	154(42%)	20(5%)	8(2%)	3(1%)	4.38	2	High	
7	Practical dimension: practicum, case studies, and internship.	159(43%)	146(40%)	34(9%)	27(7%)	3(1%)	4.17	7	High	
Mean Variable Score		4.32								

Decisions were determine using the following scoring: Very High = 4.45 to 5; High =3.45-4.44; Moderate =2.45-3.44; Low =1.45-2.44 and Strongly Very Low =1-1.44.

Source: Field Survey.

The table above shown the importance of the inclusion of some themes and concepts in the curriculum design of knowledge management for LIS education, it was revealed that the inclusion of some concepts like knowledge, knowledge management, and knowledge management process is rated high. KM themes such as knowledge management techniques, interpersonal relationships, human resources management, research and practical dimensions are also rated high. From the seven (7) concepts and themes raised, only four (4) variables score above the Mean Variable Score (X=4.32) benchmark. The interpersonal relationship leads the pacts with a mean score (X=4.39), followed by research and evaluation

with a mean score (X=4.38), Knowledge management tools, technics and technologies with a mean score (X=4.36) and lastly leadership and managerial role with a mean score (X=4.35). More emphases are placed in areas of KM not adequately taken care of by the traditional LIS curriculum and this is to say that LIS professionals are very keen on expanding their boundaries beyond traditional library practice.

The table above shows the responsibility of library schools for the acquisition of knowledge management competencies and it was agreed upon that library schools should become a major provider of knowledge

Table 4: Responsibilities of Library Schools for the acquisition of required competencies for Knowledge Management (N=369).

S/N	Library Schools Responsibilities	SA	A	N	D	SD	Mean	Rank	Decision
		F (%)	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)			
1	It is essentials that Library schools should become a major provider of knowledge management education.	196(53%)	148(40%)	12(3%)	10(3%)	3(1%)	4.43	3	Agree
2	Library schools need to cooperate with other allied disciplines in librarian for knowledge management.	215(58%)	124(34%)	11(3%)	16(4%)	3(1%)	4.44**	2	Agree
3	Library schools need to revamp, revise and reassess their curriculum continuously to keep the pace of new development in knowledge management.	173(47%) 6(2%)	151(41%)	26(7%)	13(3%)	6(2%)	4.28	4	Agree
4	Library schools need to train and retrain their educators for knowledge management.	203(55%)	143(39%)	12(3%)	7(2%)	4(1%)	4.45*	1	Strongly Agree
Mean Variable Score									4.4

Decisions were determine using the following scoring: Strongly Agree = 4.45 to 5; Agree =3.45-4.44; Neutral =2.45-3.44; Disagree =1.45-2.44 and Strongly Disagree =1-1.44.

Source: Field Survey

management education and as well collaborate with other knowledge management education providers for curriculum design, training, and teaching. It was also agreed upon that curriculum needed to be regularly revisited to keep abreast of new development in knowledge management, and finally, training and retraining (train the trainers) of LIS educators for knowledge management is of great importance for successful knowledge management education. From the four (4) variables raised on responsibilities of LIS schools, two of the variables score above the Mean Variable Score (X=4.4) benchmark. The need for LIS schools to train and retrain LIS educators score the highest mean score (X=4.45) followed by the need for LIS schools to collaborate with other allied disciplines in the design and training of LIS professionals for KM with a mean score (X=4.4). This implies that effective training and education for KM calls for cooperation and collaboration among different academic units.

5. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Findings from the study demonstrated the need for library and information science curriculum to keep changing to accommodate new development in knowledge management. This aligns with study of library and information science jobs in Sydney, where it was reported that traditional established skills of LIS professionals in job advertisement requirements over the years have decreased drastically (Kennan et al., 2006). This occurrence calls for the acquisition of more and more competencies for LIS professionals. Just in correlation with the studies above, study proclaimed that curriculum needs to be revised for a positive result that will produce a new era library and information professionals that can serve as a knowledge manager in an organization (Baghdadabad's, 2008). In a similar vein, also reported that education for LIS should change to accommodate development in knowledge management (Sarrafzadeh, 2008). It also manifested in this study that the current curriculum did not adequately equip LIS professionals for knowledge management practice. Participants attested to the fact that knowledge management can be treated as a separate course on its own and as well be integrated into the syllabus of existing library and information science courses. This correspondingly substantiates the position of who suggested that knowledge management themes and concepts should be integrated into already existing LIS courses and as well being taught as a separate course (Nwosu, 2016).

Importance of some themes and concepts as to their worthiness of inclusion in curriculum design for knowledge management education and training were examined, and concepts like knowledge, knowledge management, knowledge management process are considered important while themes like knowledge management techniques, communication and interpersonal relationship, leadership and managerial role, research and evaluation, and practical dimensions were also considered important in the content design of knowledge management for library and

information science education. More emphasis is placed on interpersonal relationships, research and evaluation as well as knowledge management tools, technics and technologies areas of knowledge management outside traditional LIS practice, which necessitate the need for cooperation and collaboration among various academic units also offering knowledge management course.

Library schools were reported to be a major provider of knowledge management education and it was agreed upon that they should collaborate with other providers of knowledge management training and education, such as business schools, computer science and information technology schools, management schools and many more for curriculum design and training for knowledge management and that effort should be made to make provision for training and retraining of trainers (educators) in library schools. This report is in congruence with survey of knowledge management education provided by members of schools of the I-schools caucus and teaching experience in Chinese library schools that also advocate for a collaborative effort from various academic units (Zhou et al., 2018).

5.1 Report of Findings from Interview

The interviewees provide insight on themes of the study that better match results from the surveyed library and information science professionals in Nigeria. Participants were asked to conceptualized knowledge management in relation to librarianship; constructive information inferred from their responses is that knowledge management is both within and outside librarianship that librarians have always been involved with the management of explicit knowledge through library collection development, knowledge organization, information/knowledge access and services. However, management of tacit knowledge (a component of knowledge management) has not been the focus of library and information science professionals and this is where divergence occurs, that they are just beginning to explore tacit knowledge management but largely in collaboration with other research entities within and outside their institutions.

On how library schools incorporate knowledge management into their curriculum, the five interviewees ascribed that it is a standalone course module even though there are other related courses such as strategic information management, record management, research method, knowledge organization, information system and many more. Four of the five interviewees noted that input from allied disciplines are needed for knowledge management content design and training for LIS students that there are allied knowledge management courses or components of it on their campuses that they do not even take cognizance of that also require auditing. The five respondents who are educators and trainers, who have

seen and experience it all demonstrated that knowledge management increase job opportunities for LIS graduate in all sector of the economy by creating new career option and also expand the prospect of LIS profession. Recommendations were given that library schools should endeavor to employ qualified staff and make provision for the training and development of the existing ones, to encourage research in the domain, to include knowledge management course in both undergraduate and postgraduate programs, identify already existing knowledge management supporting courses in the LIS curriculum and develop them, encourage awareness of knowledge management and related disciplines, encourage collaboration in teaching, learning and research, identify and develop role models and leaders in the domain, and also increase student awareness and interest.

6. CONCLUSION

Drawing from the findings of the study, the researchers concluded that there was a considerable level of interest among LIS professionals in Nigeria to embrace knowledge management in all its forms and ramifications. Emphases are placed in areas of knowledge management competencies not adequately taken care of by the traditional LIS curriculum and this is to say that LIS professionals are very keen on expanding their boundaries beyond traditional library practice. A multidisciplinary field like knowledge management requires diversified skills and knowledge, hence, the need for collaboration effort that brings the desire balance, the coverage that saves the risk of biased contents. Library schools as one of the major provider of knowledge management training and education needed to collaborate with other academic units for curriculum design and training, as some knowledge management skills and competencies were better taught by other allied professionals, such as leadership and managerial skills by management scientist, information technology skills by computer scientist, communication and interpersonal relationship by communication and cognitive scientist and many more. This collaborative effort will enable library schools to leverage the strength of other disciplines. This implies that effective training and education for knowledge management calls for cooperation and collaboration among different academic units as this will militates against unevenness of content. Be that as it may, knowledge management can be treated as a standalone course and also be integrated with the syllabus of already existing traditional library and information courses for easy and smooth assimilation.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Arising from the discussion of findings and the conclusion drawn, recommendations were given that:

1. The library and information science curriculum should keep changing to accommodate new development in knowledge management, as this will position LIS professionals for wider job expansion, even outside the four walls of the library and as well enhance their capacity to play a leadership role in an organization's knowledge management initiative.
2. Library and information science schools should collaborate with other providers of knowledge management education in curriculum design and training as some competencies of knowledge management are better taught by allied professional or academic units.
3. Library and information science educators should be exposed to periodic training and retraining that will enhance their competencies in providing KM education for new era library and information science professionals.
4. National Universities Commission of Nigeria (NUC), Nigerian Library Association (NLA) and Librarians' Registration Council (LRCN) should collaborate on the best way to develop and harmonize an acceptable standard curriculum that meets the need of the present society that was being driven by knowledge economy for library and information science education.

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